

Received-Makale Geliş Tarihi 03.08.2025
Published-Yayınlanma Tarihi 31.10.2025
Volume-Cilt (Issue-Sayı), ss/pp 12 (124),2247-2258

Research Article /Araştırma Makalesi
10.5281/zenodo.17525148

Doç. Dr. Mehmet Emin Baysal

<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-1023-4009>

Konya Teknik Üniversitesi, Mühendislik ve Doğa Bilimleri Fakültesi, Konya / TÜRKİYE
ROR Id: <https://ror.org/02s82rs08>

Doç. Dr. Ahmet Sarucan

<https://orcid.org/0000-0001-5582-2456>

Konya Teknik Üniversitesi, Mühendislik ve Doğa Bilimleri Fakültesi, Konya / TÜRKİYE
ROR Id: <https://ror.org/02s82rs08>

Endüstri Yüksek Müh. Gülçin Çam

<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-7291-8633>

Konya Teknik Üniversitesi, Lisansüstü Eğitim Enstitüsü, Konya / TÜRKİYE
ROR Id: <https://ror.org/02s82rs08>

Fuzzy Multi-Criteria Decision-Making Approach to Selecting the Most Suitable Human Resources Software in Strategic Human Resources Management

Stratejik İnsan Kaynakları Yönetiminde En Uygun İnsan Kaynakları Yazılımını Seçmek için Bulanık Çok Kriterli Karar Verme Yaklaşımı

ABSTRACT

Selecting software is a difficult MCDM problem with many conflicting criteria. With rapidly changing practices and organization needs, selecting human resources software is getting more complicated. Human resources management, whose main aim is to create value, plays an important role in creating sustainable competitive advantage. While Human resources professionals now have to contribute to the organization in the strategic roles, in recent years when digitalization is in our lives in every sense, it matters to implement human resources processes in the most effective ways. One of the aims of this study is to determine relevant evaluation criteria and to create an evaluation framework with integrated fuzzy MCDM methods by addressing the selection of the human resources software as a process. The other aim of the study is to make a contribution to the literature since the fuzzy SWARA method is not used in combination with fuzzy COPRAS and fuzzy EDAS methods in the selection of human resources software in the literature, and the resources related to the fuzzy SWARA method are limited.

Keywords: Fuzzy SWARA, Fuzzy COPRAS, Fuzzy EDAS, Multi-criteria decision-making, Human Resources Management.

ÖZET

Yazılım seçimi, birçok çelişkili kriterin olduğu zor bir MCDM problemidir. Hızla değişen uygulamalar ve organizasyon ihtiyaçları ile insan kaynakları yazılımı seçimi daha karmaşık hale gelmektedir. Ana amacı değer yaratmak olan insan kaynakları yönetimi, sürdürülebilir rekabet avantajı yaratmada önemli bir rol oynamaktadır. İnsan kaynakları uzmanları artık stratejik rollerde organizasyona katkıda bulunmak zorundadırlar. Dijitalleşmenin her anlamda hayatımıza girdiği son yıllarda, insan kaynakları süreçlerini en etkili şekilde uygulamak önem kazanmıştır. Bu çalışmanın amaçlarından biri, insan kaynakları yazılımının seçimini bir süreç olarak ele alarak, ilgili değerlendirme kriterlerini belirlemek ve entegre bulanık MCDM yöntemleriyle bir değerlendirme çerçevesi oluşturmaktır. Çalışmanın diğer amacı, literatürde insan kaynakları yazılımının seçiminde bulanık SWARA yöntemi bulanık COPRAS ve bulanık EDAS yöntemleriyle birlikte kullanılmadığından ve bulanık SWARA yöntemiyle ilgili kaynaklar sınırlı olduğundan, literatüre katkı sağlamaktır.

Anahtar Kelimeler: Bulanık SWARA, Bulanık COPRAS, Bulanık EDAS, Çok kriterli karar verme, İnsan Kaynakları Yönetimi.

1. INTRODUCTION

The development of technology and the growing number of international companies have made transformation processes an increasingly important issue. Now that the workforce is regarded as a valuable asset, human resources roles within organizations have become a function that drives change. Given the rapid changes in organizational strategies and plans, it is impossible for human resources policies and practices to remain static. Although global market conditions may present opportunities for growth, they can sometimes reduce an organization's ability to compete effectively. This means that organizations need to invest in employee development and system improvement, which in turn requires adaptation and change.

Information technology is becoming increasingly important for organizations in the digital age. This is because the need for rapid access to information is on the rise. In order to keep up with the competition, organizations need to be able to make decisions in different environments.

In the professional world, most decisions are made in uncertain and risky environments. There are many methods for selecting the best alternative when making decisions. This study employed an integrated approach, in which fuzzy MCDM methods played a pivotal role, to select the optimal alternative.

The next section presents the literature review of the MCDM methods and related software selection criteria used in this study. The subsequent section outlines the steps of the fuzzy SWARA, fuzzy COPRAS, and fuzzy EDAS methods. Section 4 includes the problem definition and solution framework. Section 5 uses various analytical approaches to examine all variables in the decision-making process, including decision-making methods, alternative research, criteria for selecting human resources software, and decision-making groups. It also compares the results of the integrated fuzzy MCDM methods and performs sensitivity analysis and scenario analysis for decision-maker groups. The final section concludes the paper.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

The presence of uncertainty in decision-making methods and the challenges associated with using these methods have led to the development of fuzzy logic extensions to classical MCDM methods.

Keršulienė et al. (2010) developed the SWARA (Stepwise Weighted Assessment Ratio Analysis) method. When using SWARA to determine the weights of the criteria, decision makers first rank the criteria from most to least important. Then, they compare each criterion with the previous one, starting with the second criterion. Kiani-Mavi et al. (2017) used the fuzzy SWARA approach in an early research investigation. They used SWARA and MOORA to select sustainable third-party reverse logistics providers in the plastic industry. Ulutaş (2019) evaluated the performance of the university website using the fuzzy SWARA and fuzzy WASPAS methods. In a subsequent study, the SWARA method was employed in conjunction with the ARAS method to address the supplier selection problem (Ulutaş, 2020).

The Complex Proportional Assessment (COPRAS) method was first introduced by Zavadskas et al. (1996). COPRAS is a multi-criteria decision-making method that calculates the importance weights of alternatives by separately evaluating the benefit and cost criteria for each alternative. This method has been the subject of extensive research in numerous fields (Karakaoğlu-Kundakçı and Işık, 2016). COPRAS is a multi-criteria decision-making method that can be used with qualitative and quantitative criteria. It also allows for the evaluation of the importance ratios of alternatives with respect to each other in percentages. This method has been demonstrated to be advantageous in terms of time and ease of use in paired comparisons when compared to AHP, which is an MCDM method that has been used extensively (Aksoy et al., 2015). Yazdani et al. (2011) presented fuzzy COPRAS. It is a process of evaluating alternatives by decision makers with linguistic variables to determine the alternative with the highest performance. Das et al. (2012) presented an integrated approach with fuzzy AHP and COPRAS to measure the performance of technical institutes. Chatterjee & Bose (2013) developed a methodology for evaluating wind farm sites by employing the fuzzy COPRAS model.

EDAS (Evaluation Based on Distance from Average Solution) is a versatile methodology that falls within the broader framework of MCDM (Multiple Criteria Decision Making). A foundational element of EDAS pertains to the evaluation of alternatives, with this evaluation being based on their proximity to the mean solution. This approach enables a systematic and objective evaluation of alternative solutions, taking into account their proximity to the optimal solution. EDAS was developed by Ghorabae et al. (2015). Ghorabae's (2016) paper proposes a fuzzy EDAS model for evaluating and selecting suppliers. Stević et al. (2018) employed fuzzy EDAS and trapezoidal fuzzy numbers for supplier selection. Stević et al. (2019) used a combined MCDM approach, integrating fuzzy AHP and EDAS, to select suppliers.

A literature search was conducted to identify criteria for selecting human resources software due to limited resources. Jadhav & Sonar (2009) provided a comprehensive overview of selection criteria. Challa et al. (2011) evaluated software quality in a fuzzy environment using ISO/IEC 9126 and their own criteria. Keil & Tiwana (2006) and Bayraktar & Efe (2006) focused on ERP software evaluation.

Table 1 shows a comprehensive overview of integrated MCDM studies employing fuzzy SWARA-fuzzy COPRAS and fuzzy SWARA-fuzzy EDAS. The studies are concentrated in 2020, but there is no study on human resources software selection or software selection among the evaluation issues.

Table 1. Literature Review

The following studies utilized the fuzzy SWARA-fuzzy COPRAS methodology:
The evaluation and ranking of solutions to mitigate sustainable remanufacturing supply chain risks employs a hybrid fuzzy SWARA-fuzzy COPRAS frame (Ansari et al., 2020).
The selection of suppliers for vendor-managed inventory in healthcare settings is a crucial decision that can be approached through the use of a fuzzy multi-criteria decision-making approach (Sumrit, 2020).
This paper proposes an integrated approach of SWARA and fuzzy COPRAS for the purpose of determining the selection factors ranking of maintenance technicians (Ighravve&Oke, 2019).
The objective of this study is to develop a novel assessment fuzzy model, with a particular emphasis on enhancing the reliability of customers' individual verbal judgments in the context of internet banking (Sadeghi & Kazemi, 2019).
Sustainable third-party reverse logistics provider evaluation and selection using SWARA and COPRAS in the presence of risk criteria (Zarbakshnia et al., 2018).
The following studies employed the fuzzy SWARA-fuzzy EDAS methodology:
A Case Study of Turnaround Project Risk Assessment Utilizing Hybrid Fuzzy SWARA and EDAS Methodology in the Context of Upstream Oil Process Industries in Iran (Moniri et al., 2020).
A novel hybrid fuzzy MCDM methodology has been proposed for the evaluation of construction equipment in consideration of sustainability (Ghorabae et al., 2018).

3. METHODS

3.1. Fuzzy SWARA

The steps of the fuzzy SWARA are as follows (Kiani-Mavi, 2017; Sumrit, 2020; Madenoğlu, 2019):

Step 1: Selected evaluation criterion ($i = 1, 2, 3, \dots, n$) are ranked from most important to least important by decisions makers (DM's)

Step 2: The relative importance value (s_j) is evaluated with linguistic variables by comparing each criterion ($j=1, 2, 3, \dots, n$) a with the previous criteria.

Step 3: Coefficient value (k_j^-) is calculated as follows.

$$k_j^- = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } j = 1 \\ s_j + 1 & \text{if } j > 1 \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

Step 4: Relative weights (q_j^-) is calculated as follows.

$$q_j^- = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } j = 1 \\ \frac{s_j - 1}{k_j^-}, & \text{if } j > 1 \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

Step 5: The relative importance weight (w_j^-) is calculated by dividing the relative weight of the each of criterion by the total relative weight values of the criteria.

$$w_j^- = \frac{q_j^-}{\sum_{k=1}^n (q_k^-)} \quad (3)$$

Step 6: The relative importance weights (w_j^-) is changed into the crisp values with *Best* nonfuzzy performance (*BNP*) as follows.

$$w_j = \frac{(w_j^u - w_j^l) + (w_j^m - w_j^l)}{3} + w_j^l \quad (4)$$

3.2. Fuzzy COPRAS

The steps of the fuzzy COPRAS are as follows (Yıldırım & Timor, 2019).

Step 1: The first step to solve the problem with the fuzzy COPRAS is to determine the criteria ($i = 1, 2, 3, \dots, n$) and alternatives ($j = 1, 2, 3, \dots, m$).

Step 2: Second step is to decide which fuzzy numbers to use, the linguistic terms and to obtain priority of DM's for alternative with linguistic terms.

Step 3: Construct the fuzzy decision matrix, x_{ijk}^- indicate importance value of alternative A_i with respect to criterion C_j evaluated by k th expert and x_{ij}^- triangle fuzzy number is shown $x_{ijk}^- = (x_{ijk}^l, x_{ijk}^m, x_{ijk}^u)$. In that case there are more than one decision makers, the fuzzy decision matrix is converted into a group decision matrix according as follows

$$x_{ij}^l = \min_k \{ x_{ijk}^l \} \quad x_{ij}^m = \frac{1}{K} \sum_{k=1}^K x_{ijk}^m \quad x_{ij}^u = \max_k \{ x_{ijk}^u \} \quad (5)$$

Step 4: Fuzzy group decision matrix is changed into the crisp group decision matrix with *Best* nonfuzzy performance (*BNP*) as follows.

$$x_{ij} = \frac{(x_{ij}^u - x_{ij}^l) + (x_{ij}^m - x_{ij}^l)}{3} + (x_{ij}^l) \quad (6)$$

Step 5: Normalize crisp group decision matrix as follows.

$$x_{ij} = \frac{x_{ij}}{\sum_{i=1}^m x_{ij}} \quad (7)$$

Step 6: The fuzzy weighted normalized matrix are calculated by multiplying the weight of criteria with normalize crisp group decision matrix.

Step 7: Sum of the benefit criteria is shown (S_{i+}), sum of the cost criteria is shown (S_{i-}) and are calculated as follows. For benefit criteria ($j = 1, 2, 3, \dots, K$) and cost criteria ($j = k + 1, k + 2, \dots, n$):

$$S_{i+} = \sum_{j=1}^k x_{ij} \quad (8)$$

$$S_{i-} = \sum_{j=1}^n x_{ij} \quad (9)$$

Step 8: Relative weights (Q_i) for each alternative is calculated as follows.

$$Q_i = S_{i+} + \frac{s - \min \sum_{i=1}^m S_{i-}}{s - i \sum_{i=1}^m \frac{s - \min}{s - i}} \quad (10)$$

Step 9: Performance weight of alternatives (P_i) is calculated as follows. It is considered that alternative has highest performance weight value is the best alternative.

$$P_i = \frac{Q_i}{Q_{max}} \times 100 \quad (11)$$

3.3. Fuzzy EDAS

The steps of the fuzzy EDAS are as follows (Keshavarz-Ghorabae, 2016).

Step 1 and 2: The first and second steps in fuzzy EDAS are the same as in fuzzy COPRAS.

Step 3: Construct the fuzzy decision matrix, x_{ijk} indicate importance value of alternative A_i with respect to criterion C_j evaluated by k^{th} expert. In that case there are more than one decision makers, fuzzy group decision matrix is calculated to average relative importance value of DM's

Step 4: For each criterion, average importance matrix [aV_j] is calculated as follows.

$$aV_j = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^m x_{ij}}{m} \quad (12)$$

Step 5: Positive distance value (*PDA*) and negative distance value (*NDA*) is calculated for benefit and cost criteria separately.

For benefit criteria, PDA and NDA is calculated as follows.

$$PDA_{ij} = \frac{\max(0, (x_{ij} - aV_j))}{aV_j} \quad (13)$$

$$NDA_{ij} = \frac{\max(0, (aV_j - x_{ij}))}{aV_j} \quad (14)$$

For cost criteria, PDA and NDA is calculated as follows.

$$PDA_{ij} = \frac{\max(0, (aV_j - x_{ij}))}{aV_j} \quad (15)$$

$$NDA_{ij} = \frac{\max(0, (x_{ij} - aV_j))}{aV_j} \quad (16)$$

Step 6: For each alternative, weighted sum of positive value (SP_i), weighted sum of negative value (SN_i) is calculated as follows.

$$SP_i = \sum_{j=1}^n w_j * PDA_{ij} \quad (17)$$

$$SN_i = \sum_{j=1}^n w_j * NDA_{ij} \quad (18)$$

Step 7: Normalized weighted sum of positive value (NSP_i) and normalized weighted sum of negative value (NSN_i) is calculated as follows.

$$NSP_i^{\sim} = \frac{SP_i^{\sim}}{\text{mak}(SP_i^{\sim})} \quad (19)$$

$$NSN_i^{\sim} = 1 - \frac{SN_i^{\sim}}{\text{mak}(SN_i^{\sim})} \quad (20)$$

Step 8: Performance of alternatives (AS_i^{\sim}) is calculated as follows.

$$AS_i^{\sim} = 1/2(NSP_i^{\sim} + NSN_i^{\sim}) \quad (21)$$

Step 9: Performance of alternatives (AS_i^{\sim}) is changed into the crisp value with *Best* nonfuzzy performance (*BNP*). It is considered that alternative has highest performance weight value is the best alternative.

4. THE PROBLEM DEFINITION AND THE PROPOSED SOLUTION FRAMEWORK

Selecting software is a difficult MCDM problem. It has many conflicting criteria, and human resources software selection is becoming more complicated due to rapidly changing practices and organization needs.

Figure 1. Proposed Solution Framework

A lack of sufficient research into alternatives and the selection criteria can lead to an unsuitable software selection. Such errors result in financial and labor losses. Errors in human resources software selection can lead to ineffective HR functions, poor employee motivation and performance, and financial losses. The variety of content and features in human resources software modules can make it hard to access detailed information. Alternatives must be investigated in detail to overcome this issue and improve the decision-making process. Another purpose of software review is to determine the evaluation criteria correctly.

5. CASE STUDY

5.1. Alternatives and Criteria

There are nine human resources software options, hereafter called A1, A2, A3, ..., A9. One (A1) is cloud-based and cost-free. Two (A2 and A9) require no web-based setup, and can be accessed via any web browser. A4, A5, A6, and A7 have custom software options. A2 and A6 are easy to implement, as they have more ready-content modules.

Some alternatives offer software that differs from human resources software, like ERP (enterprise resource planning). A1, A6, and A7 specialize in human resources software. Most group companies prefer A1, A2, A5, and A6.

Determining the relevant criteria in software selection is important in solving the problem. The main aim of examining alternatives is to make the most accurate comparison of software options. After searching the literature and examining the alternatives, it was decided to evaluate them with ten criteria.

Total cost of ownership: This paper considers the total cost of ownership to be the sum of licensing, maintenance, implementation, and setup costs. This is because there is no setup cost in cloud-based software, and implementing costs are not separate from licensing costs in most local software.

Indirect Benefit: The software improves customer service and accelerates processes (Jadhav & Sonar, 2009).

Software reputation: This paper's cost ownership criterion includes user companies' reputation and software popularity.

Technical Support Capacity: The paper's technical support capacity criterion includes the evaluation of the capacity to provide support during and after implementation. In some alternatives, like global software, the consultancy companies that implement and develop the software are different. For most global software, consultancy and development companies should be considered separately. Companies' solution partners should be included. In addition to evaluating the company's references, market position, implementation and support skills, experience of consultants to be assigned to the company, the presence of online services, should also be considered.

Sectoral experience: is a criterion for determining if a software company has customers in the same sector. Different sectors may have different human resources practices. This criterion is especially important for medium and large companies. It shows that multiple sectors and different human resources practices can be integrated under a single software system in a group company. The system can work seamlessly with a great number of employees.

Module Completeness: Defines the level of ability that covers required functions and features (Challa et al., 2011) [15]. Evaluate software functionality considering current company needs as well as future needs (Bayraktar & Efe, 2006).

Implementation Ease: The ability to easily adapt company processes to software. According to Bernroider and Koch, small and medium-sized companies prioritize this criterion over large-sized companies (Keil & Tiwana, 2006).

Attractiveness: The attractiveness criterion explains how appealing the software is. Employees can design their own user interface and access applications and information about them.

Ease of Development: The criterion defines how easily development requirements are met (Jadhav & Sonar, 2009).

Ease of Integration: The software's ability to integrate easily with other software or applications (Challa et al., 2011).

5.2. The Determination of Criteria Weights with fuzzy SWARA

Fuzzy SWARA was used to determine the criterion weights.

Step 1: There are ten criteria which is described in section 5.1, hereafter called $C_1, C_2, C_3, \dots, C_{10}$.

Step 2: First, decision-makers ranked the criteria from the criterion according to their priority from the highest importance to the lowest importance (shown in Table 3) and then compared with the previous criteria starting from the second criterion by using linguistic variables (shown in Table 2)

Table 2. Linguistic Variables

Linguistic Variables	Fuzzy Numbers (l, m, u)
Equally important (EI)	(1, 1, 1)
Moderately less important (MI)	(2/3, 1, 3/2)
Less important (LI)	(2/5, 1/2, 2/3)
Very less important (VI)	(2/7, 1/3, 2/5)
Much less important (MuI)	(2/9, 1/4, 2/7)

Table 3. Ranking of Priority

Cri.	DM ₁	DM ₂	DM ₃	DM ₄	DM ₅	DM ₆
C ₁	5	7	5	4	2	6
C ₂	6	6	6	8	3	8
C ₃	4	5	7	1	6	4
C ₄	7	4	3	6	5	1
C ₅	3	2	8	3	7	5
C ₆	1	1	1	2	1	7
C ₇	2	3	2	7	10	9
C ₈	10	8	4	10	9	10
C ₉	8	9	9	9	4	2
C ₁₀	9	10	10	5	8	3

Step 3: Coefficient value (k_j^-) is calculated using eq.(1) and is shown in Table 4.

Table 4. Coefficient Values

DM's/Cri.		C ₁	C ₂	C ₃	C ₄	C ₅	C ₆	C ₇	C ₈	C ₉	C ₁₀
DM ₁	l	1.67	1.67	2.00	1.67	1.67	1.00	1.40	1.29	1.29	2.00
	m	2.00	2.00	2.00	2.00	2.00	1.00	1.50	1.33	1.33	2.00
	u	2.50	2.50	2.00	2.50	2.50	1.00	1.67	1.40	1.40	2.00
DM ₂	l	2.00	2.00	1.29	1.40	1.67	1.00	2.00	1.40	2.00	1.67
	m	2.00	2.00	1.33	1.50	2.00	1.00	2.00	1.50	2.00	2.00
	u	2.00	2.00	1.40	1.67	2.50	1.00	2.00	1.67	2.00	2.50
DM ₃	l	2.00	1.22	2.00	2.00	2.00	1.00	1.67	1.67	1.29	1.22
	m	2.00	1.25	2.00	2.00	2.00	1.00	2.00	2.00	1.33	1.25
	u	2.00	1.29	2.00	2.00	2.00	1.00	2.50	2.50	1.40	1.29
DM ₄	l	2.00	1.40	1.00	1.67	2.00	2.00	1.67	1.29	1.40	1.29
	m	2.00	1.50	1.00	2.00	2.00	2.00	2.00	1.33	1.50	1.33
	u	2.00	1.67	1.00	2.50	2.00	2.00	2.50	1.40	1.67	1.40
DM ₅	l	2.00	1.67	2.00	1.67	1.67	1.00	1.29	2.00	1.40	2.00
	m	2.00	2.00	2.00	2.00	2.00	1.00	1.33	2.00	1.50	2.00
	u	2.00	2.50	2.00	2.50	2.50	1.00	1.40	2.00	1.67	2.00
DM ₆	l	1.67	1.67	2.00	1.00	1.67	1.67	1.40	1.22	1.67	1.67
	m	2.00	2.00	2.00	1.00	2.00	2.00	1.50	1.25	2.00	2.00
	u	2.50	2.50	2.00	1.00	2.50	2.50	1.67	1.29	2.50	2.50

Step 4: Relative weights (q_j^-) are calculated using Eq. (2) and are shown in Table 5.

Table 5. Relative Weights

DM's/Cri.		C ₁	C ₂	C ₃	C ₄	C ₅	C ₆	C ₇	C ₈	C ₉	C ₁₀
DM ₁	l	0.048	0.019	0.120	0.008	0.240	1.000	0.600	0.002	0.005	0.003
	m	0.083	0.042	0.167	0.021	0.333	1.000	0.667	0.006	0.016	0.008
	u	0.129	0.077	0.214	0.046	0.429	1.000	0.714	0.014	0.036	0.018
DM ₂	l	0.021	0.043	0.086	0.120	0.400	1.000	0.200	0.013	0.006	0.003
	m	0.031	0.063	0.125	0.167	0.500	1.000	0.250	0.021	0.010	0.005
	u	0.042	0.083	0.167	0.214	0.600	1.000	0.300	0.030	0.015	0.009
DM ₃	l	0.040	0.031	0.016	0.200	0.008	1.000	0.400	0.080	0.006	0.004
	m	0.063	0.050	0.025	0.250	0.013	1.000	0.500	0.125	0.009	0.008
	u	0.090	0.074	0.037	0.300	0.018	1.000	0.600	0.180	0.014	0.012
DM ₄	l	0.125	0.009	1.000	0.036	0.250	0.500	0.014	0.004	0.005	0.089
	m	0.125	0.016	1.000	0.047	0.250	0.500	0.023	0.008	0.010	0.094
	u	0.125	0.025	1.000	0.058	0.250	0.500	0.035	0.014	0.018	0.097
DM ₅	l	0.500	0.200	0.024	0.048	0.010	1.000	0.002	0.002	0.120	0.005
	m	0.500	0.250	0.042	0.083	0.021	1.000	0.004	0.005	0.167	0.010
	u	0.500	0.300	0.064	0.129	0.039	1.000	0.008	0.010	0.214	0.019
DM ₆	l	0.013	0.002	0.080	1.000	0.032	0.005	0.001	0.001	0.400	0.160
	m	0.031	0.008	0.125	1.000	0.063	0.016	0.005	0.004	0.500	0.250
	u	0.065	0.023	0.180	1.000	0.108	0.039	0.017	0.014	0.600	0.360

Step 5: The relative importance weight (w_j^-) is calculated using Eq. (3) and is shown in Table 6. Then the relative importance weights are combined with the arithmetic mean of the relative importance weights of decision makers.

Table 6. Relative Importance Weights

DM's/Cri.		C ₁	C ₂	C ₃	C ₄	C ₅	C ₆	C ₇	C ₈	C ₉	C ₁₀
DM ₁	l	0.018	0.007	0.045	0.003	0.090	0.374	0.224	0.001	0.002	0.001
	m	0.036	0.018	0.071	0.009	0.142	0.427	0.285	0.003	0.007	0.003
	u	0.063	0.038	0.105	0.023	0.210	0.489	0.349	0.007	0.018	0.009
DM ₂	l	0.009	0.017	0.035	0.049	0.163	0.407	0.081	0.005	0.003	0.001
	m	0.014	0.029	0.058	0.077	0.230	0.460	0.115	0.010	0.005	0.002
	u	0.022	0.044	0.088	0.113	0.317	0.529	0.159	0.016	0.008	0.005
DM ₃	l	0.017	0.013	0.007	0.086	0.003	0.430	0.172	0.034	0.002	0.002
	m	0.031	0.024	0.012	0.122	0.006	0.490	0.245	0.061	0.005	0.004
	u	0.050	0.041	0.021	0.168	0.010	0.560	0.336	0.101	0.008	0.007
DM ₄	l	0.059	0.004	0.471	0.017	0.118	0.236	0.007	0.002	0.002	0.042
	m	0.060	0.008	0.482	0.023	0.121	0.241	0.011	0.004	0.005	0.045
	u	0.062	0.012	0.492	0.029	0.123	0.246	0.017	0.007	0.009	0.048
DM ₅	l	0.219	0.088	0.011	0.021	0.004	0.438	0.001	0.001	0.053	0.002
	m	0.240	0.120	0.020	0.040	0.010	0.480	0.002	0.003	0.080	0.005
	u	0.262	0.157	0.034	0.067	0.020	0.523	0.004	0.005	0.112	0.010
DM ₆	l	0.005	0.001	0.033	0.416	0.013	0.002	0.001	0.000	0.166	0.067
	m	0.016	0.004	0.062	0.500	0.031	0.008	0.003	0.002	0.250	0.125
	u	0.038	0.014	0.106	0.590	0.064	0.023	0.010	0.008	0.354	0.212

Step 6: The relative importance weights (w_j^-) are changed into the crisp values using eq.(4). While the most important criterion is determined as C₆- Module completeness, the less important criterion is determined as C₈- Attractiveness.

Table 7. Weights of Criteria

Criteria	Weight of criteria	Ranking
C ₆	0.35	1
C ₄	0.13	2
C ₃	0.12	3
C ₇	0.11	4
C ₅	0.09	5
C ₁	0.07	6
C ₉	0.06	7
C ₂	0.03	8
C ₁₀	0.03	9
C ₈	0.01	10

5.3. Evaluating Alternatives with fuzzy COPRAS

Alternatives are evaluated by DM's via Linguistic variables (Yazdani et al., 2011) shown in Table 8.

Step 1: There are ten criteria whose weights are calculated with fuzzy SWARA in section 5.3, and nine alternatives which are mentioned in section 5.1.

Step 2: Alternatives were evaluated by DM's via Linguistic variables (Yazdani et al., 2011) shown in Table 8.

Table 8. Linguistic Variables for Alternatives

Linguistic Variables	Fuzzy Numbers (l, m, u)
Very Poor (VP)	(0, 0, 2.5)
Poor (P)	(0, 2.5, 5)
Fair (F)	(2.5, 5, 7.5)
Good (G)	(5, 7.5, 10)
Very Good (VG)	(7.5, 10, 10)

Step 3: After obtaining DM's priorities, a group decision matrix is formed using Eq. (5).

Table 9. Group Decision Matrix

Cri. /Alt.		A ₁	A ₂	A ₃	A ₄	A ₅	A ₆	A ₇	A ₈	A ₉
C ₁	l	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
	m	10.0	10.0	7.5	7.1	7.1	6.3	2.5	2.5	2.5
	u	10.0	10.0	10.0	10.0	10.0	10.0	10.0	5.0	5.0
C ₂	l	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
	m	7.9	5.4	7.5	7.5	9.2	7.9	6.3	3.3	2.5
	u	10.0	10.0	10.0	10.0	10.0	10.0	10.0	10.0	5.0
C ₃	l	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
	m	8.8	10.0	5.4	5.4	4.6	6.7	1.7	1.3	1.3
	u	10.0	10.0	10.0	10.0	7.5	10.0	7.5	7.5	7.5
C ₄	l	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
	m	8.8	7.5	5.4	5.4	6.7	7.1	4.6	4.2	4.2
	u	10.0	10.0	10.0	10.0	10.0	10.0	10.0	7.5	7.5
C ₅	l	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
	m	8.8	9.6	4.6	4.6	7.5	7.5	7.1	2.1	2.1
	u	10.0	10.0	7.5	7.5	10.0	10.0	10.0	5.0	5.0
C ₆	l	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
	m	7.9	5.4	5.0	6.7	7.9	9.6	5.0	3.3	3.3
	u	10.0	10.0	7.5	10.0	10.0	10.0	7.5	10.0	10.0
C ₇	l	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
	m	8.3	6.7	6.3	6.3	6.7	7.1	4.6	5.0	5.0
	u	10.0	10.0	10.0	10.0	10.0	10.0	7.5	10.0	10.0
C ₈	l	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
	m	9.2	5.4	5.4	5.4	7.9	6.7	5.4	5.4	2.1
	u	10.0	10.0	10.0	10.0	10.0	10.0	10.0	10.0	5.0
C ₉	l	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
	m	6.7	9.2	5.0	5.0	6.7	6.7	5.4	4.2	4.2
	u	10.0	10.0	7.5	7.5	10.0	10.0	10.0	7.5	7.5
C ₁₀	l	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
	m	9.2	10.0	5.0	5.0	7.1	6.3	5.0	4.6	4.2
	u	10.0	10.0	7.5	7.5	10.0	10.0	7.5	7.5	7.5

Step 4-5-6: The importance value of the alternative is changed into crisp values using eq.(6), the crisp group decision matrix is normalized using eq.(7), and the weighted normalized group matrix is obtained by multiplying by criterion weights.

Table 10. Weighted Normalized Crisp Decision Matrix

Al./Cri	C ₁	C ₂	C ₃	C ₄	C ₅	C ₆	C ₇	C ₈	C ₉	C ₁₀
A ₁	0.010	0.0045	0.018	0.018	0.014	0.046	0.014	0.002	0.008	0.005
A ₂	0.009	0.0037	0.019	0.016	0.014	0.039	0.013	0.002	0.008	0.005
A ₃	0.008	0.0042	0.014	0.014	0.008	0.032	0.012	0.002	0.005	0.003
A ₄	0.008	0.0042	0.014	0.014	0.008	0.042	0.012	0.002	0.005	0.003
A ₅	0.008	0.0046	0.011	0.015	0.012	0.045	0.013	0.002	0.007	0.004
A ₆	0.008	0.0043	0.016	0.016	0.012	0.050	0.013	0.002	0.007	0.004
A ₇	0.008	0.0039	0.009	0.014	0.012	0.032	0.009	0.002	0.007	0.003
A ₈	0.004	0.0032	0.008	0.011	0.005	0.034	0.011	0.002	0.005	0.003
A ₉	0.004	0.0018	0.008	0.011	0.005	0.034	0.011	0.001	0.005	0.003

Step 7: Based on Fuzzy COPRAS steps, (S_{i+}) values are calculated using eq.(8) and (S_{i-}) values are calculated using eq.(9).

Step 8-9: Relative weights (Q_i) and performance weight of alternatives (P_i) are shown in Table 11.

Table 11. Ranking Alternatives Based on P_i

Alternatives	Q _i (Relative weight)	P _i (Performance weight)
A ₁	0.13	100
A ₆	0.13	99
A ₂	0.13	95
A ₅	0.12	93
A ₄	0.11	86
A ₃	0.10	78
A ₇	0.10	74
A ₈	0.10	73
A ₉	0.09	71

5.4. Evaluating Alternatives with fuzzy EDAS

Step 1 and 2: The Fuzzy EDAS method was used to evaluate the results to compare two different MCDM methods. The same linguistic variables (Table 8) were used in the fuzzy EDAS method

Step 3: Unlike the COPRAS method, the performance priority values of decision makers were averaged while creating a fuzzy group decision matrix.

Step 4: Average importance matrix $[aV_j^-]$ is calculated using eq.(12).

Table 12. Group Decision Matrix And Average Importance Values

Cri. /Alt.		A ₁	A ₂	A ₃	A ₄	A ₅	A ₆	A ₇	A ₈	A ₉	aV _j ⁻
C ₁	l	7.5	7.5	5.0	4.6	4.6	4.6	3.8	0.0	0.0	4.2
	m	10.0	10.0	7.5	7.1	7.1	7.1	6.3	2.5	2.5	6.7
	u	10.0	10.0	10.0	9.6	9.6	9.6	8.8	5.0	5.0	8.6
C ₂	l	5.4	2.9	5.0	5.0	6.7	5.4	3.8	0.8	0.0	3.9
	m	7.9	5.4	7.5	7.5	9.2	7.9	6.3	3.3	2.5	6.4
	u	9.6	7.9	9.6	9.6	10.0	10.0	8.3	5.8	5.0	8.4
C ₃	l	6.3	7.5	2.9	2.9	2.1	4.2	0.8	0.4	0.4	3.1
	m	8.8	10.0	5.4	5.4	4.6	6.7	1.7	1.3	1.3	5.0
	u	10.0	10.0	7.9	7.9	7.1	9.2	2.7	2.3	2.3	6.6
C ₄	l	6.3	5.0	2.9	2.9	4.2	4.6	2.1	1.7	1.7	3.5
	m	8.8	7.5	5.4	5.4	6.7	7.1	4.6	4.2	4.2	6.0
	u	10.0	9.6	7.9	7.9	8.8	9.2	7.1	6.7	6.7	8.2
C ₅	l	6.3	7.1	2.1	2.1	5.0	5.0	4.6	0.0	0.0	3.6
	m	8.8	9.6	4.6	4.6	7.5	7.5	7.1	2.1	2.1	6.0
	u	10.0	10.0	7.1	7.1	10.0	10.0	9.6	4.2	4.2	8.0
C ₆	l	5.4	2.9	2.5	4.2	5.4	7.1	2.5	1.3	1.3	3.6
	m	7.9	5.4	5.0	6.7	7.9	9.6	5.0	3.3	3.3	6.0
	u	9.2	7.9	7.5	8.8	9.2	10.0	7.5	5.0	5.0	7.8
C ₇	l	5.8	4.2	3.8	3.8	4.2	4.6	2.1	2.5	2.5	3.7
	m	8.3	6.7	6.3	6.3	6.7	7.1	4.6	5.0	5.0	6.2
	u	10.0	8.3	8.8	8.8	9.2	9.2	7.1	7.5	7.5	8.5
C ₈	l	6.7	2.9	2.9	2.9	5.4	4.2	2.9	2.9	0.0	3.4
	m	9.2	5.4	5.4	5.4	7.9	6.7	5.4	5.4	2.1	5.9
	u	9.6	7.9	7.9	7.9	9.2	9.2	7.9	7.9	4.2	8.0
C ₉	l	4.2	6.7	2.5	2.5	4.2	4.2	2.9	1.7	1.7	3.4
	m	6.7	9.2	5.0	5.0	6.7	6.7	5.4	4.2	4.2	5.9
	u	8.8	10.0	7.5	7.5	9.2	9.2	7.9	6.7	6.7	8.1
C ₁₀	l	6.7	7.5	2.5	2.5	4.6	3.8	2.5	2.1	1.7	3.8
	m	9.2	10.0	5.0	5.0	7.1	6.3	5.0	4.6	4.2	6.3
	u	10.0	10.0	7.5	7.5	9.6	8.8	7.5	7.1	6.7	8.3

Step 5-6: After calculating PDA and NDA values, SP_i⁻ values are calculated using eq.(17), and SN_i⁻ values are calculated using eq. (18).

Step 7: PDA and NDA values are normalized, which are calculated separately based on fuzzy EDAS steps, and are also shown in Table 13.

Step 8-9: As AS_i⁻ values indicate fuzzy performance of alternatives, AS_i values indicate crisp performance of alternatives.

Table 13. Ranking Alternatives Based on Average Importance Values

R.	SP _i ⁻			SN _i ⁻			NSP _i ⁻			NSN _i ⁻			AS _i ⁻			AS _i
	l	m	n	l	m	n	l	m	n	l	m	n	l	m	n	
A ₁	0.0	0.4	2.1	0.0	0.0	0.8	0.0	0.2	1.0	0.6	1.0	1.0	0.3	0.6	1.0	0.6
A ₆	0.0	0.3	2.1	0.0	0.0	1.0	0.0	0.2	1.0	0.6	1.0	1.0	0.3	0.6	1.0	0.6
A ₂	0.0	0.3	1.8	0.0	0.1	1.2	0.0	0.1	0.9	0.5	1.0	1.0	0.3	0.6	0.9	0.6
A ₅	0.0	0.2	1.9	0.0	0.0	1.2	0.0	0.1	0.9	0.5	1.0	1.0	0.2	0.5	1.0	0.6
A ₄	0.0	0.1	1.7	0.0	0.1	1.6	0.0	0.0	0.8	0.3	1.0	1.0	0.1	0.5	0.9	0.5
A ₃	0.0	0.0	1.5	0.0	0.1	1.8	0.0	0.0	0.7	0.2	1.0	1.0	0.1	0.5	0.9	0.5
A ₇	0.0	0.0	1.3	0.0	0.2	1.9	0.0	0.0	0.6	0.2	0.9	1.0	0.1	0.5	0.8	0.5
A ₈	0.0	0.0	0.8	0.0	0.4	2.2	0.0	0.0	0.4	0.0	0.8	1.0	0.0	0.4	0.7	0.4
A ₉	0.0	0.0	0.8	0.0	0.4	2.3	0.0	0.0	0.4	0.0	0.8	1.0	0.0	0.4	0.7	0.4

5.5. Sensitivity Analysis

Criterion sensitivity analysis is performed to assess how the criterion weights impact the ranking in various scenarios.

Figure 2: Results of sensitivity analysis

Twenty-five experiments were run for the sensitivity analysis. In each experiment, one evaluation criterion is 0.91, while the other criteria have the lowest weight (0.01). A₁ is the best alternative in experiments 4, 7, and 8, and in general, A₁ is the best.

In experiment 11, all weights are evenly distributed, and A₁ is the best alternative. In experiments 12 through 21, the highest-weighted criterion has the highest weight (0.35), while the other criteria have evenly distributed weights of 0.07. A₁ is the best alternative, except in experiments 12 and 20. In experiment 22, the three highest weights are distributed among criteria C₃, C₄, and C₆, while the other criteria have close to 0 weight. A₁ is the best alternative, and A₆ is the second best. In experiments 23 through 25, the three highest weights are calculated as close to 1, while the other criteria have close to 0 weight. The best alternative is A₁, and the sensitivity analysis results are shown in Figure 2.

5.6. Scenario Analysis

The effectiveness of decision-making is influenced by those who make it, and six decision makers were chosen to solve a given problem. Different evaluations of individual and group decisions are examined using scenarios. The first scenario examines group decisions made by managers, and the second by non-manager decision makers.

Scenario 1: The case of managers making decisions is examined. The steps in sections 5.2 and 5.3 are followed to examine the group decision of managers formed by DM₁, DM₅, and DM₆.

Table 14. Best Alternative Ranking for DM₁, DM₅ And DM₆

Alternatives	Qi (Relative weight)	Pi (Performance weight)
A ₆	0.14	100
A ₁	0.14	99
A ₅	0.13	95
A ₂	0.12	90
A ₄	0.11	83
A ₇	0.10	76
A ₃	0.10	74
A ₈	0.09	65
A ₉	0.09	63

As indicated in Table 14, Alternative A₆ demonstrates the highest performance value, followed by Alternative A₁ and Alternative A₅, which exhibits the third highest performance value.

Scenario 2: The case that decision makers consist only of employees is examined.

Sections 5.2 and 5.3 detail the steps to examine the group decision of the non-managers formed by DM₂, DM₃, and DM₄.

Table 15. Best Alternative Ranking for DM₂, DM₃ and DM₄

Alternatives	Qi (Relative weight)	Pi (Performance weight)
A ₁	0.14	100
A ₆	0.13	97
A ₂	0.13	94
A ₅	0.12	89
A ₄	0.11	83
A ₃	0.10	76
A ₈	0.10	70
A ₉	0.09	69
A ₇	0.09	68

As seen in Table 15, the alternative with the highest performance index weight is A₁, then A₆ and the alternative with the third highest performance is A₂.

6. CONCLUSION

This study uses the fuzzy SWARA method to calculate criterion weights evaluated by decision makers. This method has fewer pairwise comparisons than other MCDM methods, which is a key reason for its use. The fuzzy SWARA method is a newer method than other MCDM methods, and there are few studies on it. It is also thought to contribute to the literature. The most important criterion is C6-Module Completeness, the second most important is C4-Technical Support Capacity, and the least important is C8-Attractiveness. With the fuzzy COPRAS method, decision makers evaluate alternatives according to specified criteria. The best alternative is A₁, and the second best is A₆. Since their performance weights are very close, a different method, fuzzy EDAS, is used to compare the results. The results are similar, and 25 experiments are run for sensitivity analysis to see how different weight of criterion affect the results. Figure 2 shows that most experiments indicate that A₁, A₆, and A₂ have the highest performance weight. When the first and second scenarios are examined, different rankings are made.

This study shows that examining all software in detail and searching customer experiences for alternatives can improve decision efficiency.

The results of the rankings using both methods are very close, and the results of the scenario analysis support this. A shortlist could be created based on the evaluation results. The top four or five alternatives could be ranked again.

A group evaluation in a workshop, where all decision-makers are present, is one other suggestion. Comparing the results from two institutions with constraints like cost and location is an example.

REFERENCES

- Aksoy, E., Ömürbek, N., & Karaatlı, M. (2015). AHP Temelli MULTIMOORA ve COPRAS Yöntemi ile Türkiye Kömür İşletmeleri'nin Performans Değerlendirmesi. *Hacettepe Üniversitesi İktisadi ve İdari Bilimler Fakültesi Dergisi*, 33(4), 1-28. <https://doi.org/10.17065/huiibf.10920>
- Ansari, Z. N., Kant, R., & Shankar, R. (2020). Evaluation and ranking of solutions to mitigate sustainable remanufacturing supply chain risks: a hybrid fuzzy SWARA-fuzzy COPRAS framework approach. *International Journal of Sustainable Engineering*, 13(6), 473–494. <https://doi.org/10.1080/19397038.2020.1758973>
- Bayraktar, E., & Efe, M. (2006). Kurumsal kaynak planlaması ERP ve yazılım seçim süreci. *Selçuk Üniversitesi Sosyal Bilimler Enstitüsü Dergisi* (15), 689-709.
- Challa, J. S., Paul, A., Dada, Y., Nerella, V., Srivastava, P. R., & Singh, A. P. (2011). Integrated Software Quality Evaluation: A Fuzzy Multi-Criteria Approach. *Journal of Information Processing Systems*, 7(3), 473–518. <https://doi.org/10.3745/JIPS.2011.7.3.473>
- Chatterjee, N. & Bose, G. (2013). A COPRAS-F-based multi-criteria group decision making approach for site selection of wind farm. *Decision Science Letters*. 2. 1-10. 10.5267/j.dsl.2012.11.001.
- Das, M., Sarkar, B. & Ray, S. (2012). A framework to measure relative performance of Indian technical institutions using integrated fuzzy AHP and COPRAS methodology. *Socio-Economic Planning Sciences*. 46. 230–241. 10.1016/j.seps.2011.12.001.
- Ghorabae, M.K., Amiri, M., Zavadskas, E.K. & Antucheviciene, J. (2018). A new hybrid fuzzy MCDM approach for evaluation of construction equipment with sustainability considerations. *Archiv.Civ.Mech.Eng* 18, 32–49. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.acme.2017.04.011>
- Ighravwe, D. & Oke, S. (2019). An integrated approach of SWARA and fuzzy COPRAS for maintenance technicians' selection factors ranking. *International Journal of System Assurance Engineering and Management*. 10. 10.1007/s13198-019-00912-8.
- Jadhav, Anil & Sonar, Rajendra. (2009). Evaluating and selecting software packages: A review. *Information and Software Technology*. 51. 555-563. 10.1016/j.infsof.2008.09.003.

- Karakaşoğlu-Kundakcı, N. & Işık, A. (2016). Integration of MACBETH and COPRAS methods to select air compressor for a textile company. *Decision Science Letters*. 5. 381-394. 10.5267/j.dsl.2016.2.003.
- Keil, M. & Tiwana, A. (2006). Relative importance of evaluation criteria for enterprise systems: A conjoint study. *Inf. Syst. J.* 16. 237-262. 10.1111/j.1365-2575.2006.00218.x.
- Keršulienė, V., Zavadskas, E. & Turskis, Z. (2010). Selection of rational dispute resolution method by applying new step-wise weight assessment ratio analysis (SWARA). *Journal of Business Economics and Management - J BUS ECON MANAG.* 11. 10.3846/jbem.2010.12.
- Keshavarz-Ghorabae, M., Zavadskas, E., Amiri, M. & Turskis, Z. (2016). Extended EDAS Method for Fuzzy Multi-criteria Decision-making: An Application to Supplier Selection. *International Journal of Computers Communications & Control*. 11. 358-371. 10.15837/ijccc.2016.3.2557.
- Kiani-Mavi, R., Goh, M. & Zarbakhshnia, N. (2017). Sustainable third-party reverse logistic provider selection with fuzzy SWARA and fuzzy MOORA in plastic industry. *The International Journal of Advanced Manufacturing Technology*. 91. 10.1007/s00170-016-9880-x.
- Madenöđlu, F. (2019). Bulanık çok kriterli karar verme ortamında yeşil tedarikçi seçimi. *Business & Management Studies: An International Journal*. 7. 1850-1869. 10.15295/bmij.v7i4.1155.
- Moniri, M., Alam T. A., Ayough, A. & Zandieh, M. (2020). Turnaround project risk assessment using hybrid fuzzy SWARA and EDAS method: case of upstream oil process industries in Iran. *Journal of Engineering, Design and Technology*. ahead-of-print. 10.1108/JEDT-07-2020-0287.
- Sadeghi, H. & Kazemi, F. (2019). Developing a new assessment fuzzy model by focusing on improving the reliability of customers' individual verbal judgment (An Internet Banking case study). *Consumer Behavior Studies Journal*, 5(2), 55-82.
- Stević, Ź., Vasiljević, M., Zavadskas, E., Sremac, S. & Turskis, Z. (2018). Selection of carpenter manufacturer using fuzzy EDAS method. *Engineering Economics*. 29. 281-290. 10.5755/j01.ee.29.3.16818.
- Stević, Ź., Vasiljević, M., Puška, A., Tanackov, I., Junevičius, R. & Vesković, S. (2019). Evaluation of suppliers under uncertainty: A multiphase approach based on fuzzy ahp and fuzzy edas. *Transport*. 34. 52-66. 10.3846/transport.2019.7275.
- Sumrit, D. (2020). Supplier selection for vendor-managed inventory in healthcare using fuzzy multi-criteria decision-making approach. *Decision Science Letters*. 9. 233-256. 10.5267/j.dsl.2019.10.002.
- Ulutaş, A. (2019). University Website Performance Evaluation Using Fuzzy SWARA and WASPAS-F. *Multi-Criteria Decision-Making Models for Website Evaluation* (pp.151-165), IGI Global.
- Ulutaş, A. (2020). Using of Fuzzy SWARA and Fuzzy ARAS Methods to Solve Supplier Selection Problem. *Theoretical and Applied Mathematics in International Business*.10.4018/978-1-5225-8458-2.ch008.
- Yazdani, M. & Alidoosti, A. & Zavadskas, E. (2011). Risk Analysis of Critical Infrastructures Using Fuzzy Copras. *Ekonomika Istrazivanja*. 24. 27-40. 10.1080/1331677X.2011.11517478.
- Yıldırım, B. F., & Timor, M. (2019). Bulanık ve Gri COPRAS Yöntemleri Kullanılarak Tedarikçi Seçim Modeli Geliştirilmesi. *Optimum Ekonomi ve Yönetim Bilimleri Dergisi*, 6(2), 283-310. <https://doi.org/10.17541/optimum.548505>
- Zarbakhshnia, N., Soleimani, H. & Ghaderi, H. (2018). Sustainable Third-Party Reverse Logistics Provider Evaluation and Selection Using Fuzzy SWARA and Developed Fuzzy COPRAS in the Presence of Risk Criteria. *Applied Soft Computing*. 65. 10.1016/j.asoc.2018.01.023.